

Nonspecific reaction in ELISA of viruses in rice roots

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Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) has been routinely used to detect rice viruses. An initial test of rice roots indicated that many apparently healthy plants collected from IRRI fields reacted positively for rice ragged stunt virus (RRSV). We examined whether a nonspecific reaction or false positive reaction occurs in ELISA of different rice plant parts.

We tested 18 healthy 3- to 9-wk-old TN1 plants. Seedlings were kept in a screen cage and sprayed with cypermethrin 5 wettable powder at 2 and 6 wk to prevent rice virus infections. Plant samples were collected weekly and subdivided into leaf blades, leaf sheaths, culms, and roots.

Samples were weighed, homogenized in 10X volume of 0.02 M phosphate buffer solution Tween, and assayed by double antibody sandwich (DAS)-ELISA

Number of healthy plants showing positive reaction^a in ELISA using 4 virus antisera.

Plant age ^b (wk)	Plants (no.)							
	Culms				Roots			
	RTBV	RTSV	RRSV	RGSV	RTBV	RTSV	RRSV	RGSV
5	0	0	0	0	7	7	2	3
6	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
8	2	1	—	—	2	3	—	—
9	1	7	1	0	8	17	8	4

^aPositive reaction defined as >0.05 of ELISA value and >3× the negative mean of healthy leaf blades at 10-d-old seedling stage. No virus was detected in leaf blades and sheath. ^bNo virus was detected in any plant parts at 3 and 4 wk.

using four virus antisera: rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV), rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV), RRSV, and rice grassy stunt virus (RGSV). Four plants, each infected with a virus, served as controls.

Rice viruses were not detected in leaf blades and leaf sheaths throughout the experiment, indicating that all plants were healthy. But some root samples of the 5- and 9-wk-old plants tested positive for all four virus antisera (see table).

Mean ELISA absorbance values of positive reactions for root samples obtained during weeks 5 and 9 were 0.17 for RTBV, 0.36 for RTSV, 0.36 for

RRSV, and 0.18 for RGSV; values for samples from infected plants were 0.45 for RTBV, 0.64 for RTSV, 1.06 for RRSV, and 0.33 for RGSV. Only a few root samples at 6, 7, and 8 wk and a few culm samples at 8 and 9 wk showed positive reactions.

The obtained ELISA values were low compared with those from infected roots. Results suggest that nonspecific reactions in ELISA—not caused by the virus—occurred when rice roots were tested. ELISA data from leaves and healthy roots should accompany data for virus-infected roots to accurately interpret results. □

Pest resistance—insects

Resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) in rice germplasm in Raipur, Madhya Pradesh (MP), India

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Five hundred germplasm accessions from Madhya Pradesh Rice Research Institute (MPRRI) were screened for resistance to BPH *Nilaparvata lugens*. Susceptible TN1 and resistant Ptb 33 were used as check varieties.

We sowed seed in wooden seedboxes in the greenhouse during 1989–90. Ten-d-old seedlings were uniformly infested with second- to third-instar BPH nymphs. Damage for all entries was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when TN1 died. Entries scoring <3 were retested several times. We selected 13 resistant varieties for evaluation of BPH honeydew excretion.

Two-day-old BPH females (starved for 5 h) were caged in a chamber at the base

of 35-d-old plants. During the next 24 h, BPHs excreted blue honeydew spots on bromocresol green-treated filter paper on the chamber floor.

All 13 varieties restricted the BPH feeding rate, which was 0.96 to 6.32 mm²/female. The feeding rate was heavy (192 mm²/female) on susceptible TN1

(see table). The low feeding rate indicates that resistant plants have feeding-deterrent or antifeedant chemicals.

Each female excreted extremely low amounts of honeydew on Chapdo (0.96 mm²), Pandari Ajan (1.24 mm²), and Bakawa (5.34 mm²). These varieties suggest the possibility of ecogenetic diversity in Bastar district. □

Resistance of MPRRI rice germplasm to BPH. Raipur (MP), India.

Variety	Damage score ^a	Honeydew excreted in 24 h (mm ² /female)	Seed origin (district)
Chapdo	1.5	0.96	Bastar
Bundiyanbanko	1.7	5.29	Raipur
Barhi	2.2	1.96	Mandla
Dhaura Basan	2.4	3.01	Damoh
LalBasant	1.5	5.55	Jabalpur
Bakiya	2.4	6.52	Chhatarpur
Ama Koyali	0.6	3.47	Rajnandgaon
Agyasal	1.6	2.04	Raigarh
Pandari Ajan	1.2	1.24	Bastar
Lal Basant	1.5	5.65	Jabalpur
Bataroo	2.1	6.00	Narsinghpur
Bhakawa	1.7	5.34	Bastar
Chhatri	1.6	3.30	Gwalior
PTB33 (resistant check)	1.6	6.8	
TN1 (susceptible check)	9.0	192.0	

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale 0–9.